

Some inequalities concerning Smarandache's function

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The objectives of this article are to study the sum $\sum_{d|n} S(d)$ and to find some upper

bounds for Smarandache's function. This sum is proved to satisfy the inequality

$\sum_{d|n} S(d) \leq n$ at most all the composite numbers. Using this inequality, some new

upper bounds for Smarandache's function are found. These bounds improve the well-known inequality $S(n) \leq n$.

1. Introduction

The object that is researched is Smarandache's function. This function was introduced by Smarandache [1980] as follows:

$$S: N^* \rightarrow N \text{ defined by } S(n) = \min\{k \in N \mid k! = \underline{Mn}\} \quad (\forall n \in N^*). \quad (1)$$

The following main properties are satisfied by S :

$$(\forall a, b \in N^*) (a, b) = 1 \Rightarrow S(a \cdot b) = \max\{S(a), S(b)\}. \quad (2)$$

$$(\forall a \in N^*) S(a) \leq a \text{ and } S(a) = a \text{ iff } a \text{ is prim.} \quad (3)$$

$$(\forall p \in N^*, p \text{ prime})(\forall k \in N^*) S(p^k) \leq p \cdot k. \quad (4)$$

Smarandache's function has been researched for more than 20 years, and many properties have been found. Inequalities concerning the function S have a central place and many articles have been published [Smarandache, 1980], [Cojocaru, 1997], [Tabirca, 1997], [Tabirca, 1988]. Two important directions can be identified among these inequalities. First direction and the most important is represented by the inequalities concerning directly the function S such as upper and lower bounds. The second direction is given by the inequalities involving sums or products with the function S .

2. About the sum $\sum_{d|n} S(d)$

The aim of this section is to study the sum $\sum_{d|n} S(d)$.

Let $SS(n) = \sum_{d|n} S(d)$ denote the above sum. Obviously, this sum satisfies

$SS(n) = \sum_{1 \neq d|n} S(d)$. Table 1 presents the values of $S(n)$ and $SS(n)$ for $n < 50$ [Ibstedt,

1997]. From this table, it can be seen that the inequality $SS(n) \leq n + 2$ holds for all $n = 1, 2, \dots, 50$ and $n \neq 12$. Moreover, if n is a prim number, then the inequality becomes equality $SS(n) = n$.

Remarks 1.

a) If n is a prime number, then $SS(n) = S(1) + S(n) = n$.

b) If $n > 2$ is a prim number, then

$$SS(2 \cdot n) = S(1) + S(2) + S(n) + S(2 \cdot n) = 2 + n + n = 2 \cdot n + 2,$$

c) $SS(n^2) = S(1) + S(n) + S(n^2) = n + 2 \cdot n = 3 \cdot n \leq n^2$.

N	S	SS												
1	0	0	11	11	11	21	7	17	31	31	31	41	41	41
2	2	2	12	4	16	22	11	24	32	8	24	42	7	36
3	3	3	13	13	13	23	23	23	33	11	25	43	43	43
4	4	6	14	7	16	24	4	24	34	17	36	44	11	39
5	5	5	15	5	13	25	10	15	35	7	19	45	6	25
6	3	8	16	6	16	26	13	28	36	6	34	46	23	48
7	7	7	17	17	17	27	9	18	37	37	37	47	47	47
8	4	10	18	6	20	28	7	27	38	19	40	48	6	36
9	6	9	19	19	19	29	29	29	39	13	29	49	14	21
10	5	12	20	5	21	30	5	28	40	5	30	50	10	32

Table 1. The values of n , S , SS .

The inequality $SS(n) \leq n$ is proved to be true for the following particular values $n = p^k, 2 \cdot p^k, 3 \cdot p^k$ and $6 \cdot p^k$.

Lemma 1. If $p > 2$ is a prime number and $k > 1$, then the inequality $SS(p^k) \leq p^k$ holds.

Proof

The following inequality holds according to inequality (4) and the definition of SS .

$$SS(p^k) = \sum_{i=1}^k S(p^i) \leq \sum_{i=1}^k p \cdot i = p \cdot \frac{k \cdot (k+1)}{2}.$$

The inequality

$$\sum_{i=1}^k p \cdot i = p \cdot \frac{k \cdot (k+1)}{2} \leq p^k \quad (5)$$

is proved to be true by analysing the following cases.

$$\bullet \quad k=2 \Rightarrow 3 \cdot p \leq p^2. \quad (6)$$

$$\bullet \quad k=3 \Rightarrow 6 \cdot p \leq p^3. \quad (7)$$

$$\bullet \quad k=4 \Rightarrow 10 \cdot p \leq p^4. \quad (8)$$

Inequalities (6-8) are true because $p > 2$.

$$\bullet \quad k > 4 \Rightarrow p^k \geq p \cdot p^{k-1} \geq p \cdot 2^{k-1} = p \cdot \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} \binom{k-1}{i}. \quad \text{The first and the last three terms}$$

of this sum are kept and it is found

$$p^k \geq p \cdot \left(2 \cdot \binom{k-1}{0} + 2 \cdot \binom{k-1}{1} + 2 \cdot \binom{k-1}{2} \right) = p \cdot (k^2 - k + 2). \quad \text{The inequality}$$

$$k^2 - k + 2 \geq \frac{k \cdot (k+1)}{2} \text{ holds because } k > 4, \text{ therefore } p^k \geq p \cdot \frac{k \cdot (k+1)}{2} \text{ is true.}$$

Therefore, the inequality $S(p^k) \leq p^k$ holds. ♣

Remark 2. The inequality $S(p^k) \leq p^k$ is still true for $p=2$ and $k > 3$ because (8) holds for these values. Table 1 shows that the inequality is not true for $p=2$ and $k=2,3$.

Lemma 2. If $p > 2$ is a prime number and $k > 1$, then the inequality $SS(2 \cdot p^k) \leq 2 \cdot p^k$ holds.

Proof

The definition of SS gives the following equation

$$SS(p^k) = S(2) + \sum_{i=1}^k S(p^i) + \sum_{i=1}^k S(2 \cdot p^i).$$

Applying the inequality $S(2 \cdot p^i) \leq p \cdot i$ and (4), we have

$$SS(2 \cdot p^k) \leq 2 + \sum_{i=1}^k p \cdot i + \sum_{i=1}^k p \cdot i = 2 + p \cdot k \cdot (k+1). \quad (9)$$

The inequality

$$2 + p \cdot k \cdot (k+1) \leq 2 \cdot p^k \quad (10)$$

is proved to be true as before.

$$\bullet \quad k=2 \Rightarrow 2 + 6 \cdot p \leq 2 \cdot p^2. \quad (11)$$

$$\bullet \quad k=3 \Rightarrow 2 + 12 \cdot p \leq 2 \cdot p^3. \quad (12)$$

$$\bullet \quad k=4 \Rightarrow 2 + 20 \cdot p \leq 2 \cdot p^4. \quad (13)$$

$$\bullet \quad k=5 \Rightarrow 2 + 30 \cdot p \leq 2 \cdot p^5. \quad (14)$$

$$\bullet \quad k=6 \Rightarrow 2 + 42 \cdot p \leq 2 \cdot p^5. \quad (15)$$

These above inequalities (11-15) are true because $p > 2$.

$$\bullet \quad k > 6 \Rightarrow p^k \geq p \cdot p^{k-1} \geq p \cdot 2^{k-1} = p \cdot \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} \binom{k-1}{i}. \quad \text{The first and the last four terms}$$

of this sum are kept finding

$$\begin{aligned} p^k &\geq p \cdot \left(2 \cdot \binom{k-1}{0} + 2 \cdot \binom{k-1}{1} + 2 \cdot \binom{k-1}{2} + 2 \cdot \binom{k-1}{3} \right) \geq \\ &\geq p \cdot \left(2 \cdot \binom{k-1}{0} + 2 \cdot \binom{k-1}{1} + 2 \cdot \binom{k-1}{2} + 2 \cdot \binom{k-1}{2} \right) = \\ &= p \cdot (2 \cdot k^2 - 4 \cdot k + 4) \geq 2 + p \cdot (k^2 + k) \end{aligned}$$

The last inequality holds because $k > 6$, therefore $2 \cdot p^k \geq 2 + p \cdot k \cdot (k+1)$ is true.

The inequality $SS(2 \cdot p^k) \leq 2 \cdot p^k$ holds because (10) has been found to be true.

✦

Remark 3. Similarly, the inequality $SS(3 \cdot p^k) \leq 3 \cdot p^k$ can be proved for all ($p > 3$ and $k \geq 1$) or ($p=2$ and $k \geq 3$).

Lemma 3. If $p > 3$ is a prime number and $k \geq 1$, then the inequality $SS(6 \cdot p^k) \leq 6 \cdot p^k$ holds.

Proof

The starting point is given by the following equation (16)

$$SS(6 \cdot p^k) = S(2) + S(3) + S(6) + \sum_{i=1}^k S(p^i) + \sum_{i=1}^k S(2 \cdot p^i) + \sum_{i=1}^k S(3 \cdot p^i) + \sum_{i=1}^k S(6 \cdot p^i). \quad (16)$$

The inequalities $S(p^i), S(2 \cdot p^i), S(3 \cdot p^i), S(6 \cdot p^i) \leq p \cdot i$ hold for all $i > 1$ because $p \geq 5$. Therefore, the inequality

$$SS(6 \cdot p^k) \leq 8 + \sum_{i=1}^k p \cdot i = 8 + 4 \cdot \sum_{i=1}^k p \cdot i \quad (17)$$

holds. The inequality $SS(6 \cdot p^k) \leq 8 + 4 \cdot p^k \leq 6 \cdot p^k$ is found to be true by applying (5) in (17).

♣

The following propositions give the main properties of the function SS . Let $d(n)$ denote the number of divisors of n .

Proposition 1. If a is natural numbers such that $S(a) \geq 4$, then the inequality $S(a) \geq 2 \cdot d(a)$ holds.

Proof

The proof is made directly as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} S(a) &= \sum_{1 \neq d: a} S(d) = \sum_{1, n \neq d: a} S(d) + S(a) \geq \sum_{1, n \neq d: a} 2 + S(a) = 2 \cdot (d(a) - 2) + S(a) = \\ &= 2 \cdot d(a) + S(a) - 4 \geq 2 \cdot d(a). \end{aligned} \quad \clubsuit$$

Remark 4. The inequality $S(a) \geq 4$ is verified for all the numbers $a \geq 4$ and $a \neq 6$.

Proposition 2. If a, b are two natural numbers such that $(a, b) = 1$, then the inequality $SS(a \cdot b) \leq d(a) \cdot SS(b) + d(b) \cdot SS(a)$ holds.

Proof

This proof is made by using (2) and the simple remark that $a, b \geq 0 \Rightarrow \max\{a, b\} \leq a + b$.

The set of the divisors of ab is split into three sets as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \{1 \neq d \mid a \cdot b = \underline{M}d\} = \\ & \{1 \neq d \mid a = \underline{M}d\} \cup \{1 \neq d \mid b = \underline{M}d\} \cup \{d_1 d_2 \mid a = \underline{M}d_1 \neq 1 \wedge b = \underline{M}d_2 \neq 1 \wedge (d_1, d_2) = 1\}. \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

The following transformations hold according to (18).

$$\begin{aligned} SS(a \cdot b) &= \sum_{\{1 \neq d \mid a \cdot b = \underline{M}d\}} S(d) = \sum_{\{1 \neq d \mid a = \underline{M}d\}} S(d) + \sum_{\{1 \neq d \mid b = \underline{M}d\}} S(d) + \sum_{\{1 \neq d_1 \mid a = \underline{M}d_1\}} \sum_{\{1 \neq d_2 \mid b = \underline{M}d_2\}} S(d_1 \cdot d_2) = \\ &= SS(a) + SS(b) + \sum_{\{1 \neq d_1 \mid a = \underline{M}d_1\}} \sum_{\{1 \neq d_2 \mid b = \underline{M}d_2\}} \max\{S(d_1), S(d_2)\} \leq \\ &\leq SS(a) + SS(b) + \sum_{\{1 \neq d_1 \mid a = \underline{M}d_1\}} \sum_{\{1 \neq d_2 \mid b = \underline{M}d_2\}} [S(d_1) + S(d_2)] = \\ &= SS(a) + SS(b) + \sum_{\{1 \neq d_1 \mid a = \underline{M}d_1\}} \sum_{\{1 \neq d_2 \mid b = \underline{M}d_2\}} S(d_1) + \sum_{\{1 \neq d_1 \mid a = \underline{M}d_1\}} \sum_{\{1 \neq d_2 \mid b = \underline{M}d_2\}} S(d_2) = \\ &= SS(a) + SS(b) + SS(a) \cdot [d(b) - 1] + SS(b) \cdot [d(a) - 1] \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, the inequality $SS(a \cdot b) \leq d(a) \cdot SS(b) + d(b) \cdot SS(a)$ holds. \clubsuit

Proposition 3. If a, b are two natural numbers such that $S(a), S(b) \geq 4$ and $(a, b) = 1$, then the inequality $SS(a \cdot b) \leq SS(a) \cdot SS(b)$ holds.

Proof

Proposition 1-2 are applied to prove this proposition as follows:

$$S(a), S(b) \geq 4 \Rightarrow S(a) \geq 2 \cdot d(a) \text{ and } S(b) \geq 2 \cdot d(b) \quad (19)$$

$$(a, b) = 1 \Rightarrow SS(a \cdot b) \leq d(a) \cdot SS(b) + d(b) \cdot SS(a). \quad (20)$$

The proof is completed if the inequality $d(a) \cdot SS(b) + d(b) \cdot SS(a) \leq SS(a) \cdot SS(b)$ is found to be true. This is given by the following equivalence

$$d(a) \cdot SS(b) + d(b) \cdot SS(a) \leq SS(a) \cdot SS(b) \Leftrightarrow$$

$$d(a) \cdot d(b) \leq [SS(a) - d(a)] \cdot [SS(b) - d(b)].$$

This last inequality holds according to (19).

Therefore, the inequality $SS(a \cdot b) \leq SS(a) \cdot SS(b)$ is true. \clubsuit

Theorem 1. If n is a natural number such that $n \neq 8, 12, 20$ then

$$\text{a) } SS(n) = n + 2 \text{ if } (\exists p \text{ prime}) n = 2 \cdot p. \quad (21)$$

$$\text{b) } SS(n) \leq n, \text{ otherwise.} \quad (22)$$

Proof

The proof of this theorem is made by using the induction on n .

Equation (21) is true according to Remark 1.a. Table 1 shows that Equation (22) holds for $n < 51$ and $n \neq 8, 12, 20$. Let $n > 51$ be a natural number. Let us suppose that Equation (9) is true for all the number k that satisfies $k < n$ and k does not have the form $k = 2p$, p prime. The following cases are analysed:

- n is prime $\Rightarrow SS(n) = n$, therefore Equation (9) holds.
- $n = 2p$, $p > 2$ prime $\Rightarrow SS(n) = n + 2$, therefore Equation (21) holds.
- $(n = 2^k \text{ and } k > 3)$ or $(n = p^k \text{ and } k > 1)$ $\Rightarrow SS(n) \leq n$ according to Lemma 1
- $n = 2 \cdot p^k$, $p > 2$ prime number and $k > 1$ $\Rightarrow SS(n) \leq n$ according to Lemma 2.
- $n = 3 \cdot p^k$, ($p > 3$ prime number and $k > 1$) or ($p = 2$ and $k > 2$) $\Rightarrow SS(n) \leq n$ according to Remark 3.
- $n = 6 \cdot p^k$, $p > 3$ prime number and $k \geq 1$ $\Rightarrow SS(n) \leq n$ according to Lemma 3.
- **Otherwise** \Rightarrow Let $n = p_1^{k_1} \cdot p_2^{k_2} \cdot \dots \cdot p_s^{k_s}$ be the prime number decomposition of n with $p_1 < p_2 < \dots < p_s$. We prove that there is a decomposition of $n = ab$, $(a, b) = 1$ such that $S(a), S(b) \geq 4$. Let us select $a = p_s^{k_s}$ and $b = p_1^{k_1} \cdot p_2^{k_2} \cdot \dots \cdot p_{s-1}^{k_{s-1}}$. It is not difficult to see that this decomposition satisfies the above conditions. The induction's hypotheses is applied for $a, b < n$ and the inequalities $SS(a) \leq a$ and $SS(b) \leq b$ are obtained. Finally, Proposition 3 gives $SS(n) = SS(a \cdot b) \leq SS(b) \cdot SS(a) \leq b \cdot a = n$.

We can conclude that the inequality $SS(n) \leq n - 2$ holds for all the natural number $n \neq 12$.

Remark 5. The above analysis is necessary to be sure that the decomposition of $n = ab$, $(a, b) = 1$, $S(a), S(b) \geq 4$ exists.

Theorem 1 has some interesting consequences that are presented in the following. These establish new upper bounds for Smarandache's function.

Consequence 1. If $n > 1$ is a natural number, then the following inequality

$$S(n) \leq n + 4 - 2 \cdot d(n) \quad (23)$$

holds.

Proof

The proof of this inequality is made by using Theorem 1.

Obviously, (23) is true for $n=p$ or $n=2p$, p prime number.

Let $n \neq 8, 12, 20$ be a natural number.

We have the following transformations:

$$\begin{aligned} n \geq SS(n) &= \sum_{1 \neq d|n} S(d) = S(n) + \sum_{1, n \neq d|n} S(d) \geq \\ &\geq S(n) + 2 \cdot \left| \left\{ d = \overline{1, n} \mid d \neq 1, n \wedge d \mid n \right\} \right| = S(n) + 2 \cdot (d(n) - 2) = S(n) + 2 \cdot d(n) - 4 \end{aligned}$$

Inequality (23) is also satisfied for $n=8, 12, 20$.

Therefore, the inequality $S(n) \leq n + 4 - 2 \cdot d(n)$ holds. \clubsuit

Consequence 2. If $n > 1$ is a natural number, then the following inequality holds

$$S(n) \leq n + 4 - \min\{p \mid p \text{ is prime and } p|n\} \cdot d(n). \quad (24)$$

Proof

This proof is made similarly to the proof of the previous consequence by using the following strong inequality $S(d) \geq \min\{p \mid p \text{ is prime and } p|n\}$. \clubsuit

3. Final Remark

Inequalities (23 - 24) give some generalisations of the well - known inequality $S(n) \leq n$. More important is the fact that these inequalities reflect. When n has many divisors, the value of $n + 4 - \min\{p \mid p \text{ is prime and } p|n\} \cdot d(n)$ is small, therefore the value of $S(n)$ is small as well according to Inequality (24). In spite of fact that Inequalities (23 - 24) reflect this situation, we could not say that the upper bounds are the lowest possible. Nevertheless, they offer a better upper bound than the inequality $S(n) \leq n$.

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